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DISTINCTIVE FEATURES OF THE TURKISH INVESTMENT POLICY

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Abstract: this article analyzes the role and features of investment policy in the Turkish economy.

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The most important period of development of the current Turkish investment policy dates back to the mid-80s, which primarily serves as an integral part of reforms in the context of large-scale economic liberalization. During this period, the existing legal documents that stimulate the attraction of foreign investment have been improved and new manifestations of them have been developed. According to it, in accordance with the current legislation, the amounts transferred to the national capital were fully applied to foreign investors, and the share of foreign investors in any form of activity was not limited.

For several decades, Turkey has had liberal procedures for regulating the activities of foreign capital, additions were added and improved in accordance with the economic direction of the country in different periods.

Today, the Turkish government is taking various incentive measures against foreign investors. In particular, first of all, attention is paid to the distribution of investments by sectors, which is supported by investments in export-oriented areas of the oriali industry and knowledge-intensive industries. In addition, the support of foreign capital in Turkey in accordance with the policy of leveling the levels of economic development in certain regions of the country is of territorial importance.

It is worth noting that the Turkish economy has declined somewhat due to the pandemic, and the state of development of investment policy has become slower. In particular, in Turkey, the volume of gross domestic product decreased by 9.9% in the second quarter of 2020. This is the highest level of decline recorded since 1998. That is, according to the Turkish Statistical Institute, the

country's economy experienced a 3% year-on-year decline in the fourth quarter of 2018. Considering that in the third quarter of 2018, the country's GDP decreased by 1.6%, Turkey officially entered a recession zone, and the country's economy fell into recession. However, in September last year, the Central Bank of Turkey raised the key rate from 17.7% to 24% per annum. This was followed by an appreciation of the Turkish lira against the US dollar.

Indeed, in the implementation of the country's investment policy, the industry or sphere of the economy occupies an important place. Accordingly, the level of economic development of the territories for Turkey will be allocated separately, and if different levels of investment support are considered, they will be distributed among the following regions (Fig. 1.)

Figure 1. Grouping of regions by different levels of investment support in Turkey In the figure, mainly the regions of the most important level include the well-developed regions of Turkey on the eastern sides.

The normal regions are the western and partially central regions of the country. Developed regions are such major cities as Istanbul, Ankara, Izmir, Kocaeli, Adan and Bursa.

In addition, the territorial aspect is important in the implementation of investment policy in Turkey. The territorial location of the projected object and the amount of invested capital are the main indicators for investors to receive an incentive certificate. This certificate entitles you to use the benefits during the implementation of the project. In particular, it will consist in partial or full exemption from customs duties and taxes, as well as the possibility of obtaining preferential loans and state subsidies.

Turkey has established tax incentives for invested capital. In fact, the incentive certificate allows him to provide discounts on the payment of corporate tax. The deduction for the payment of tax to him is the location of the ZOS object, which can range from 30 to 100 percent, depending mainly on the sector of the economy and the amount of capital invested. In this case, full tax exemption is determined by the fact that the investor has the right not to pay corporate tax until he fully covers the fixed capital.

A plan has been drawn up to stimulate the capital invested in the country, and in accordance with it, the dominant sectors of the economy will consist of the following areas:

- large-scale capital investments in construction and infrastructure in regions where tourism business is developed;
- shipbuilding, ship repair and development of the leather industry;
- increasing the productivity of the agricultural and agro-industrial sectors;
- Organization of fishing farms;
- reform of the education and health system;
- Environmental protection;
- intensive development of the electronic, chemical and automotive industries.

Foreign investments in most sectors of the Turkish economy do not affect the receipt of an incentive certificate. This applies to well-established production facilities in Turkey, where stimulating investment in them will only cause excessive competition and overproduction.

Along with this, there is a system of preferential lending in Turkey. The low interest rate, high inflation in the country and the constant decline in the exchange rate of the Turkish currency against international currencies indicate that the loan provided to foreign investors is in a favorable position. They mainly use capital investments in production, where individual benefits are intended for export. For example, if within 5 years after the implementation of the project with an incentive investment certificate, the company achieves the export of a certain part of the total volume of products. And they are completely exempt from taxes, various fees and interest on the loan.

In order to stimulate investments and their rational distribution, the Government undertakes to pay 25% of the electricity consumed, 50% of the Social Insurance Fund, as well as 100% of payments to be sent to the pension fund over a five-year period. In such cases, only investments aimed at the implementation of major projects in the "most important" and "normal" regions are envisaged.

The flow of foreign investment directly to Turkey is typical. The policy of attracting foreign capital on this gave its results in a short period of time. Currently, there are more than 5,000 companies with foreign capital operating in Turkey by order number. However, this indicator of the inflow of foreign direct investment is low, which does not correspond to the economic potential of the country and its real needs.

Turkey's official circles assess Turkey's need for such investments at least once a year. Foreign direct investment is at a low level, about \$1 billion a year. amounts to dollars. In addition, a significant part of these tools will be spent on additional financing of the projects in which they work.

Turkey's entry into the Customs Union (CU) in the European Union (EU) has become an additional incentive for foreign investors. In particular, large companies from Japan, South Korea and other countries are rushing to invest in Turkey in order to import their products to EU markets without customs duties. These are primarily automobile companies such as TOYOTA, HONDA, HYUDAY, KIA, FIAT and RENAULT.

The flow of foreign direct investment to Turkey comes mainly from EU countries. The Netherlands, Germany, the United Kingdom and the United States invest the most in the Turkish economy. However, Turkey has a number of problems that displace foreign investors.

Also, non-tariff trade barriers are one of the serious factors hindering the flow of investment flows into the country. After the country's accession to the WTO, the customs department was replaced by the State Institute of Norms and Standards "TSE". Multinational corporations producing their products in all regions of the world are forced to pass the TSE and receive a Turkish quality certificate, which will take a lot of time and tools to obtain.

Portfolio investments occupy a special place in the Turkish economy. More than 20 years ago, many residents of Turkey knew little about the stock market, about the stock market. It is required to create appropriate documents and commissions in accordance with the development of the capital market. In 1982, the Capital Market Committee was established, which was charged with regulating and controlling the primary and secondary securities market of Turkey. Later, this market developed and began to be implemented in cities. In this regard, the Istanbul stock market is a very liquid market. The daily trading volume on the Istanbul Stock Exchange is sometimes \$1 billion. it comes to a dollar.

In general, the investment policy of Turkey as a component of the country's economy is of particular importance, and under the influence of all important sectors of the economy and its important elements, the investment policy will continue to develop and improve.

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